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Antimicrobial activity of epidermal mucus from *Channa punctatus*

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Fishes live in aquatic environment where they continuously encounter many pathogenic, opportunistic, and non-pathogenic microbes. The first line of defense against these microbes is the epidermis. The epidermis contains mucus-producing cells such as goblet cells or mucus cells, sacciform cells, pavement cells, etc., producing epidermal mucus. Epidermal mucus is a mixture of mucin, water, glycoproteins and other bioactive macromolecules. Bioactive macromolecules and glycoproteins of mucus provide antiviral, antibacterial, and antifungal properties to the mucus. *Channa punctatus* is a member of Channidae family which means they can breathe air through their gills, and they are commonly found on swamps and brackish water. Their habitat triggers some immune response which causes production of more antimicrobial proteins on their surface, where their air breathing nature supports the extraction of mucus outside water without killing them. Our study observed the antimicrobial activity of epidermal mucus of “*Channa punctatus*” against eight microbes that are either pathogenic or opportunistic to humans. Fish was procured from the local fish market and acclimatized at room temperature for 48h. Further it was starved for 24h before collecting mucus and mucus was extracted on 10% acetic acid solvent. Antagonistic activity test was performed to observe the antimicrobial activity in terms of zone of inhibition (ZOI). Maximum activity was observed against *Staphylococcus aureus*, whereas minimum action against *Bacillus licheniformis*. The concentration of antimicrobial proteins in epidermal mucus was 0.25mg/ml in *Channa punctatus* determined by Bradford assay using BSA as standard plot.

Keywords: Channa punctatus; Epidermal mucus; Antimicrobial proteins